

1 **Nestin possesses functions in CNS migratory behavior in humans with solid malignancy of the**
2 **breast and lung.**

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7 We studied tissue gene expression in humans with solid tumors to more closely understand the biological
8 processes by which tumor cells migrate from the lung and breast to the brain. Here we describe
9 differential expression of nestin, an intermediate filament thought to possess expression restricted to the
10 central nervous system, both during transformation of the tissue of origin and migration to the central
11 nervous system in humans with non-small cell lung cancer and breast cancer. In humans with lung
12 cancer, nestin was silenced during transformation of the lung to primary tumor; during disease progression
13 from primary tumor to CNS metastasis, nestin repression was even more marked. Stepwise analysis of
14 CNS migratory behavior revealed that in humans with breast cancer, nestin was similarly silenced during
15 transformation of the breast, and even more significant silencing when comparing primary tumor to CNS
16 metastasis, but that nestin expression was induced in circulating tumor cells isolated from the peripheral
17 blood of humans with metastatic breast cancer, and strongly activated in metastatic cells residing in the
18 lymph node. Nestin activation and repression generally correlated with CD44 expression indicating
19 changes in epithelial-mesenchymal program during metastasis are linked with nestin expression and
20 stem-like status of the tumor cell. Nestin is likely a relevant actor in CNS migratory behavior in humans
21 with solid tumor disease (cancer).
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We used whole transcriptome technologies to study expression of nestin, an intermediate filament protein, in humans with two leading causes of death from cancer, lung cancer (NSCLC, non-small cell adenocarcinoma of the lung) and breast cancer. We began this study when we observed relative silencing of nestin in humans with NSCLC; repression of nestin during transformation was of interest to us as nestin is already believed to possess CNS-restricted expression, suggesting low expression of nestin was important for structural or other cellular changes during transformation.

Results

Figure 1a: Nestin repression defines the NSCLC gene expression signature.

Cohort 1: GSE74706

ID	p-value	t	B	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P103672	9.60E-06	5.35	3.1990843	NES	2437/34183	92.9

Cohort 2: GSE33532

ID	p-value	t	B	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	1.19E-14	10.1086626	22.884138	NES	1374/25906	94.7

Cohort 3: GSE43458

ID	p-value	t	B	Gene	Rank	%DE
7921088	7.70e-11	7.6390624	14.364928	NES	899/33252	97.3

Figure 1b: Nestin repression defines the NSCLC gene expression signature.

Cohort 1: GSE74706

ID	logFC	Gene
A_23_P103672	1.64	NES

Cohort 2: GSE33532

ID	logFC	Gene
218678_at	1.527074	NES

Cohort 3: GSE43458

ID	logFC	Gene
7921088	0.56367231	NES

Nestin was among the genes whose expression changed most significantly in the transcriptome when comparing normal lung and primary tumor of the lung (Figure 1A), and its expression decreased during transformation (Figure 1B; positive logFC indicates a relative decrease in expression).

We next studied expression of nestin in the embryonic and post-natal murine lung to understand changes in nestin expression during mammalian lung development (Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 2: Nestin repression is observed during embryonic development in the lung.

Nestin expression was significantly decreased in the non-branching regions of the embryonic lung at E11.5 when compared to the branching regions (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Developmental stage-specific expression of nestin in the mammalian lung.

Nestin was expressed in a stage-specific manner in the embryonic and adult mouse lung and its expression increased during postnatal life (Figure 3). Together the data demonstrated that during transformation of the lung, nestin repression was a signature transcriptional change when comparing primary tumor and normal lung, and that changes and differences in nestin expression were normal features of the embryonic lung and associated with changes in gene expression during mammalian development.

We next examined changes in nestin expression in the breast, measuring total expression in normal, non-transformed breast and in primary tumors from patients with breast cancer of three separate subtypes: luminal A, luminal B and HER2+.

Figure 4: Nestin is repressed during transformation of the breast in humans with breast cancer.

GSE45827: Luminal A breast cancer (normal breast is reference transcriptome).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	3.21E-10	8.26	13.104484	3.1313855	NES	2112/29873	92.9
217523_at	1.12E-10	-8.59	14.149402	-2.8401468	CD44	1785/	94.0

GSE45827: Luminal B breast cancer.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	3.59E-11	8.8834992	15.20939	3.1845716	NES	1362/29873	95.4
1557905_s_at	2.71E-05	-4.7141387	1.77966	-1.8425517	CD44	7886/29873	73.6

GSE45827: HER2+ breast cancer.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	3.02E-09	7.481972	10.70965	3.7025313	NES	3514/29873	74.8
1557905_s_at	8.61E-10	-7.869586	11.96475	-2.5201957	CD44	3058/29873	89.8

We found that, like in NSCLC, nestin expression was repressed during transformation of the normal breast to primary tumor: in luminal A, luminal B and in HER2+ subtype breast cancer (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Nestin expression is activated during metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.

GSE30480: Tumor cells isolated from lymph node metastasis of humans with breast cancer (primary tumor is reference transcriptome).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P103672	1.23E-03	-3.786728	-0.82359	-0.20874053	NES	731/40991	98.2

In sorted cells from lymph node metastasis, nestin expression was activated and the magnitude of its induction was significant (Figure 5).

Figure 6: Nestin expression is activated during metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.

GSE44408: Lymph node metastases from humans with breast cancer (bulk metastasis; primary tumor is reference transcriptome)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	4.87E-01	-0.7026612	-5.8902	-0.10644357	NES	10237/22277	54.0

GSE10893: Lymph node metastases from humans with breast cancer (bulk metastasis; primary tumor is reference transcriptome)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
2008	3.42E-01	-0.9557505	-5.3779	-0.25103622	NES	6797/18034	62.3

In two separate lymph node metastasis cohorts, the expression of nestin in bulk lymph node metastasis was moderately increased (Figure 6). The data confirmed that while nestin expression decreased during transformation from normal breast to primary tumor, that during disease progression and metastasis to the lymph nodes, nestin expression markedly increased, indicating changes in nestin expression were likely important during disease progression.

Since we found an increase in nestin expression in lymph node metastasis, we examined total expression in circulating tumor cells to determine whether nestin was induced during circulation of tumor cells in the periphery (peripheral blood) during metastasis to distant organ sites via the lymph nodes.

Figure 7: Nestin expression is modestly but significantly induced during migration and circulation in the periphery in circulating tumor cells from humans with stage IV breast cancer.

GSE113890: Circulating tumor cell isolated from the blood (breast cancer): (peripheral blood is reference transcriptome)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10763	6.19E-03	0.918	-2.737395	-2.5123831	62.66	NES	8267/21908	62.3
960	5.07E-08	0.668	5.4487146	3.6387197	743.91	CD44	902/21908	95.9

Activation of NES, albeit modest, in the circulating tumor cell was concomitant with silencing of CD44, indicating dynamic modulation of nestin expression occurred together with changes in stem cell state which themselves occur simultaneously with metastatic progression and the epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT). Thus, nestin expression appeared to be directly or indirectly associated with stem cell state and EMT during metastasis.

Finally, since we observed a pattern of nestin expression modulation that appeared to track with disease progression, decreasing during transformation, then increasing during migration in the periphery and metastasis to the lymph nodes, we examined total expression in CNS metastases from humans with breast cancer to determine if a subsequent change in nestin expression was an important transcriptional event during metastasis and disease progression.

1 **Figure 8:** Nestin expression is silenced during metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer.

2 GSE191230: CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer (primary tumor is reference transcriptome)

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10763	7.81E-02	0.5025	1.7617569	0.88520547	2069.35	NES	8245/21403	61.5

5 GSE52604: CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer (primary tumor is reference transcriptome)

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ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P103672	1.56E-06	5.4939756	4.959859	1.1146571	NES	1656/41093	96.0

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8 Nestin silencing or repression in CNS metastasis, which we interpreted to be an event immediately
9 following its induction during metastasis to the lymph nodes and circulation in the periphery, argued
10 functional relevance of nestin expression change in supporting or facilitating some basic element that
11 favors or promotes CNS metastasis. These changes occurred in parallel with changes in CD44
12 expression, supporting simultaneous dynamic progression of the stem cell expression program together
13 with a progression program involving elements including nestin.

14 Discussion

15 We demonstrated here that in humans with lung cancer and humans with breast cancer, an
16 intermediate filament protein thought to possess CNS-restricted expression, nestin was among the genes
17 whose expression changed most significantly during transformation of the lung and of the breast. IN both
18 cases, its expression decreased during transformation, suggesting nestin silencing was important during
19 early transformation events in vivo. Nestin expression was strongly induced in lymph node metastases in
20 humans with breast cancer, and modestly increased in circulating tumor cells in humans with stage IV
21 breast cancer, indicating its expression was subsequently increased during migration to the periphery.
22 Nestin appears to be important for metastatic progression in breast cancer; its expression correlates
23 negatively with distant metastasis-free survival in humans with breast cancer (data not shown). During
24 metastasis to the CNS, an event we have demonstrated is closely linked to lymph node metastasis, its
25 expression was again repressed. Nestin is important for cellular shape and structure in cells of the CNS,
26 and likely plays a similar role during transformation and metastasis in humans with solid tumor malignancy
27 of the lung and breast.
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Methods

We used R-based computational methods with the datasets below to study changes in nestin expression through the solid tumor life cycle in humans with cancer of the lung and breast.

Datasets utilized

GSE45827: normal breast to luminal A primary breast
GSE45827: normal breast to luminal B primary breast
GSE45827: normal breast to HER2+ primary breast

GSE30480: (sorted cells) primary breast tumor vs LN (lymph node)
GSE44408: bulk tumor primary breast vs LN
GSE10893: bulk tumor primary breast vs LN

GSE113890: normal peripheral blood vs. circulating tumor cell isolated from the blood (stage IV breast cancer)

GSE191230: primary brain to CNS metastasis (breast)
GSE52604: primary brain to CNS metastasis (breast)

GSE74706: normal lung to primary lung tumor
GSE33532: normal lung to primary lung tumor
GSE43458: normal lung to primary lung tumor